

**“THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS FOR STUDIES ON
ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION OF B.ED. PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS”**

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Abstract:

We generally assume that procrastination is simply matter of willpower but an actual reason for which someone procrastinates is far more complex and psychological. The Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has made engaging in procrastination easier, even when a given activity is loved by students. Research has shown that this long period of physical distancing, reductions in social communication, and changes to learning formats have contributed to reduced engagement in studies among students, as well as increases in procrastination behaviors (Jia et al., 2020), and psychological distress levels (Maia and Dias, 2020). Therefore, the importance of studying these aspects at the time of the pandemic is necessary. In this study, the researcher has dealt with three psychological factors Stress, habit, and anxiety to study their effect on the academic procrastination for Preservice teachers (B. ED) of Mumbai University.

Key words: *Academic procrastination, stress, habit, attitude*

Introduction:

From Ancient times our great Rishis have warned us about the demerits of procrastination and merits of punctuality/promptitude. According to an adage in great epic Mahabharata, Procrastination is one of the six shortcomings which must be overcome if one desires to be very rich and famous. षड् दोषाः

पुरुषेणेह हातव्या भूतिमिच्छता।निद्रा तन्द्रा भयं क्रोधः आलस्यं दीर्घसूत्रता।। महाभारत उद्योग पर्व (33/78)¹

.Those persons who desire to be very rich and famous must renounce these six demerits in them, viz. excessive sleep, drowsiness, fear, anger, laziness, and the habit of procrastination.

We generally assume that procrastination is simply matter of willpower but an actual reason for which some one procrastinates is far more complex and psychological. Research over time have shown the causes and effects of procrastination in many sectors and sections of society mainly students at college level. Pre-service teachers are also affected by various psychological factors which result into their academic procrastination. This procrastination in turn impacts their academic performance also in many ways. In this study, the

researcher has dealt with three psychological factors Stress, habit, and anxiety to study their effect on the academic procrastination for Pre- Service teachers (B. ED) of Mumbai University.

Definition of Procrastination by Western Pundits

Two common definitions of procrastination are “the purposive delay in the beginning and/or completion of an overt or covert act, typically accompanied by subjective discomfort” (Ferrari, 1998, p. 281) and “to voluntarily delay an intended course of action despite expecting to be worse off for the delay” (Steel, 2007, p. 66)². These two definitions reflect the assumptions that procrastination is something that an individual is knowingly doing, and that it is a dysfunctional form of delaying. Research shows that 15% to 20% of the general population chronically procrastinates (Harriott and Ferrari, 1996; Steel, 2007)³.

These numbers are even more pronounced in the academic context, where 80% to 95% of university students report having procrastinated at least one time (Ellis and Knauss, 1977; Harriott and Ferrari, 1996), and 46% of students report procrastinating frequently on academic activities (Solomon and Rothblum, 1984). However, research has shown that academic procrastination has negative consequences with respect to students’ academic performance and life satisfaction (Balkis, 2013; Goroshit and Hen, 2019)⁴.

Researchers have also observed that procrastination in the academic domain may result in negative consequences to student’s mental health, such as anguish and discomfort due to time passing while tasks remain incomplete, perceptions of incompetence, as well as unpleasant feelings such as anxiety and guilt (Kerbaux, 2001)⁵. These negative thoughts and emotions may impair students’ learning and academic performance (Sampaio and Bariani, 2011)⁶. In relation to reasons why students are procrastinating, Solomon and Rothblum (1984)⁷ found that students appear to procrastinate on tasks that they do not like. Based on these results one may presume the students procrastinate when facing academic activities perceived as unpleasant.

The Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has made engaging in procrastination easier, even when a given activity is loved by students. As of April 2020, academic activities in India started to be carried out in virtual environment to meet the World Health Organization’s (WHO) recommendations of physical distancing, demanding important adaptations from students, professors, and other professionals from the academic community. In this sense, research has shown that this long period of physical distancing, reductions in social communication, and changes to learning formats contributed to reduced engagement in studies among students, as well as increases in procrastination behaviors (Jia et al., 2020)⁸, and psychological distress levels (Maia and Dias, 2020). Therefore, the importance of studying these aspects at the time of the pandemic is also necessary.

The present study

The present study had two objectives. The first objective was to critically evaluate the psychological factors (Stress, Habit, Attitude) affecting the academic procrastination of preservice teachers of B.ED. programme of Mumbai University. The second objective was to study the association in Psychological Factors of

Academic Procrastination according to age groups (in years) of preservice teachers of B.ED. programme of Mumbai University. A sample size of 511 B. ED. preservice teachers of batch (2018-2020) was considered for the research which included both Aided and Non-aided B. ED colleges of University of Mumbai. Two tools were used for data collection, one standardized tool (APSS) of (Solomon & Rothblum, 1984) containing 12 items of Areas of Academic Procrastination, another tool was constructed based on factors affecting Academic Procrastination. Content validity of the tool was done by 15 Ph. D experts/guides from University of Mumbai. Google form containing questionnaires was prepared and the link mailed to the students for collecting data.

CRONBACH'S ALPHA TEST:

Test of reliability of scale: This test is used for validation of Likert scale used in the questionnaire. To validate the scale in this study Cronbach Alpha test is applied. Test is applied for all 511 respondents. Following table represents the results of the test:

Variable Name	No. of subgroups	Cronbach's Alpha Result
Academic Procrastination	12	0.727
Psychological Factors		
Stress	5	0.729 Scale is reliable and accepted
Habit	5	0.735 Scale is reliable and accepted
Attitude	5	0.701 Scale is reliable and accepted

Descriptive Statistics

Stress	511	20.00	100.00	41.10	15.40
Habit	511	20.00	100.00	44.28	16.09
Attitude	511	20.00	92.00	38.74	14.95
Psychological factors	511	20.00	94.67	41.38	13.40

Presentation of Table and Interpretation

HYPOTHESIS I

Null Hypothesis H_{01A}: There is no significant difference in the Psychological Factors affecting the Academic Procrastination and Average Academic Procrastination.

Alternate Hypothesis H_{11A}: There is a significant difference in the Psychological Factors affecting the Academic Procrastination and Average Academic Procrastination.

Table 1: To test the above Null Hypothesis Paired t-test is applied, the p-value is calculated and is shown in the below table:

Paired Samples Test							
		Paired Differences			T	df	p-value
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean			
Academic Procrastination (Standard)	Psychological factors	30.04	16.14	0.71	42.07	510	0.000**

NOTE: ** denotes significant at 1% value

Interpretation: The p-value for the above pair is 0.000. This is less than 0.05. Hence the Paired t-test is rejected for these pairs. Hence Null Hypothesis is rejected and Alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion: There is a significant difference in the Psychological Factors affecting the Academic Procrastination and Average Academic Procrastination.

Finding is that the Psychological Factors affecting the Academic Procrastination is significantly different from the Average Standard Academic Procrastination. The Average Standard Academic Procrastination is higher as compared to the Psychological Factors. This can also be seen in the below table:

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Academic Procrastination (Standard)	71.42	511	8.93	0.39
	Psychological factors	41.38	511	13.40	0.59

The above table indicates that the mean score for the Average Standard Academic Procrastination is higher at 71.42 percent, while the mean score for Psychological factors is lowest at 41.38 percent. This can be graphically presented in the Bar chart as follows:

HYPOTHESIS II

Null Hypothesis H_{02A}: There is no significant difference in the Psychological Factors of Academic Procrastination according to the Age group of respondents.

Alternate Hypothesis H_{12A}: There is a significant difference in the Psychological Factors of Academic Procrastination according to the Age group of respondents.

Table 2: To test the above Null Hypothesis ANOVA is obtained and F-test is applied. Results are shown in the table below:

ANOVA					
Psychological factors					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Between Groups	78.13	2	39.06	0.21	0.80
Within Groups	91568.73	508	180.25		
Total	91646.87	510			

Interpretation: The above results indicate that calculated p-value is 0.80. It is more than 0.05 that is more than at 5% level. Therefore F-test is accepted. Hence Null hypothesis is accepted and Alternate hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion: There is no significant difference in the Psychological Factors of Academic Procrastination according to the Age group of respondents.

Finding is that the difference in the Mean Score for Psychological Factors of Academic Procrastination is highly insignificant across the Age groups of respondents. It is similar for all respondents irrespective of their age group. This can be observed in the following table:

Report			
Psychological factors			
Age group	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Up to 25 years	41.65	336	13.35
26 to 40 years	40.87	163	13.55
Above 40 years	40.44	12	13.80
Total	41.38	511	13.40

The above table indicates that the mean score for Psychological Factors of Academic Procrastination is highest at 41.65 percent for respondents aged up to 25 years, while it is lowest at 40.44 percent for respondents aged above 40 years. This verifies our findings. This can be graphically represented in a Bar chart as follows:

Conclusion:

From the results of the research and discussion that has been described, conclusions can be drawn, that; the Psychological Factors affecting the Academic Procrastination is significantly different from the Average Standard Academic Procrastination. The Average Standard Academic Procrastination is higher as compared to the Psychological Factors. The difference in the Mean Score for Psychological Factors of Academic Procrastination is highly insignificant across the Age groups of respondents. It is similar for all respondents irrespective of their age group.

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